

SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF THE MESH-FREE RANDOM GRID METHOD FOR MEASURING DEFORMATION FIELDS ON COMPOSITES

A. Iliopoulos^{1,2}, J.G. Michopoulos²

¹ Science Applications International Corporation at Naval Research Laboratory,
Code 6394, Washington DC 20375, USA
athanasios.iliopoulos.ctr.gr@nrl.navy.mil

² Computational Multiphysics Systems Laboratory, Code 6394, Center for
Computational Material Science, U.S. Naval Research Laboratory, Washington,
DC 20375, USA
john.michopoulos@nrl.navy.mil

SUMMARY

We are presenting a sensitivity analysis to assess the performance of the mesh free random grid method for the non-contact measurement of displacement and strain fields associated with the deformation of composite materials. This is motivated by the need to establish a design specification for its application on material characterization.

Keywords: Strain measurement, Displacement measurement, Composites, Anisotropic medium, Digital Imaging, Mesh free, Random Grid, Material characterization.

INTRODUCTION

In responding to the needs of the composite material characterization community [1-9], we have recently developed a mesh-free random grid method (MFRGM) for the non-contact measurement of displacement and strain fields [10-14]. The method is based on digital image processing. It has been exhibiting very promising characteristics of accuracy, adaptability, implementation flexibility, efficiency and cost. However, in order to address the issue of defining the design specification of the method according to the intended application for composite structures, we are presenting here a sensitivity analysis that aids into determining the effects of the experimental and computational parameters characterizing the MFRGM in terms of its performance.

There are two sets of parameters that affect the performance characteristics of MFRGM for whole field strain measurement applications [14]. The first set involves parameters associated with the characteristics of the experimental setup and the random grid applied on the specimen under measurement. The second set involves the computational characteristics of the mesh-free approximation and the solution (minimization) algorithms utilized. The performance characteristics of the MFRGM are mainly its accuracy, sensitivity, smoothing properties and efficiency. In the present paper we are presenting a classification of the first set of parameters as well as their relationship followed by the above mentioned sensitivity analysis to establish the influence trends in

the performance characteristics with the intention to optimize the selection of the user controlled variables for a desired performance specification.

This paper is divided into two sections. In the first section MFRGM is briefly outlined for full field displacement and strain measurements and the metric parameterization of its performance is established. In the second section the results of a sensitivity analysis of the method on synthetically created sequence of images of an orthotropic laminate with a circular hole under deformation are presented.

THE MESH FREE RANDOM GRID METHOD

In order to accomplish whole field measurement of strain fields the MFRGM requires a procedure involving the following four essential steps [10-14]:

1. A specimen is prepared by marking it with a random distribution of black dots at the area of interest.
2. Images of non-deformed and deformed specimen are acquired and a simple labelling algorithm is used to identify the centres of the dots (centroids) on each image.
3. A point matching algorithm identifies the correspondence between centroids of the dots between the two images and calculates the respective displacements.
4. The centroid displacement values previously obtained are used to calculate the full-field values of displacement and strain through mesh-free functions.

In the last step there are various choices from typical Mesh Free functions [15], including Moving Least Square (MLS) method for shape function construction and Point Interpolation methods. In this paper the shape function is constructed through the MLS method.

Metric parameterization

Since MFRGM is acting on images, the parameters affecting it relate to those that are represented by an image. Namely those are the light intensity of the image, usually represented by a number ranging within the quantization bit depth (i.e. 0 to 255 for 8-bit images) and the geometrical characteristics of the components that represent the objects of interest.

The geometrical characteristics of the objects of interest, which in the case of MFRGM are random dot markings can be distinguished into two categories. Dot characteristics, like its area and overall characteristics like the density of the dot pattern.

It is easy to identify metric representation of those characteristics. If we consider that the dot markings are mostly circular, we can study the effect of their area by using their radius in pixels. Similarly the pattern density can be parameterized by the mean dot distance, either locally or globally depending on whether the pattern is homogeneous. An extended discussion relative to those parameters can be found in [14].

ANALYSIS OF MFRGM APPLICATION ON SYNTHETICALLY DEFORMED IMAGES

In order to investigate the performance sensitivity of MFRGM, we created artificial images of a medium under deformation. The artificial medium is represented by a set of nodes and an analytic dot function.

The main goal is to fully define an analytic image, then deform it and finally digitize it on a per cell integration manner.

The simulation process is comprised by the following steps [8]:

1. Define an analytic Dot function
2. Create a synthetic distribution of dots that can be considered within the domain of a digital image.
3. Apply a digitization procedure over the analytical image to produce a digital image.
4. Deform the distribution of dots and produce a new set distribution.
5. Go to step 3 until desired number of frames are generated.

The digitization procedure is accomplished through the numerical integration of light intensity over the coverage area of the CCD cell as described elsewhere [14]. This procedure physically adds the appropriate noise level relative to the characteristics of the simulated cameras' bit depth, by introducing an artificial digitization cutoff limit of the light intensity.

The deformation of the dot distribution has been defined by adding the displacement vector to the initial coordinates of the centroids of the dots. The displacement vector is computed from the displacement field generated by the analytic solution of the boundary value problem of interest. In the present case this is described in the following section.

Anisotropic medium with an open hole

The simulation model consists of an infinitely large anisotropic elastic plate that contains a circular hole of radius r and is subjected to a stress state at infinity equal to p as shown in Fig. 1. The applied load forms an angle α with the axis the major orthotropic axis Ox . This angle essentially controls the degree of anisotropy introduced in the strain-stress fields and varying it amounts to rotating the major orthotropic axis relative to the loading direction (i.e. dual description of the angle). The general solution to this problem for an elliptic hole is known [16] and is specialized here to reflect the

Figure 1: Anisotropic infinite plate with circular hole and load at infinity.

problem with a circular hole. Additional modifications have been introduced [17] to account for rotations at infinity.

Strain at any point on the plane is given by the constitutive equations:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{xx} &= a_{11}\sigma_{xx} + a_{12}\sigma_{yy} + a_{16}\tau_{xy} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} &= a_{12}\sigma_{xx} + a_{22}\sigma_{yy} + a_{26}\tau_{xy} \\ \gamma_{xy} &= a_{16}\sigma_{xx} + a_{26}\sigma_{yy} + a_{66}\tau_{xy} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

Where stresses are calculated by the equations:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_{xx} &= \sigma_{xx}^{\infty} + 2 \operatorname{Re} \left[s_1^2 \frac{\partial \varphi_0(z_1)}{\partial z_1} + s_2^2 \frac{\partial \psi_0(z_2)}{\partial z_2} \right] \\ \sigma_{yy} &= \sigma_{yy}^{\infty} + 2 \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{\partial \varphi_0(z_1)}{\partial z_1} + \frac{\partial \psi_0(z_2)}{\partial z_2} \right] \\ \tau_{xy} &= \tau_{xy}^{\infty} - 2 \operatorname{Re} \left[s_1 \frac{\partial \varphi_0(z_1)}{\partial z_1} + s_2 \frac{\partial \psi_0(z_2)}{\partial z_2} \right] \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

at the above equations, s_1, s_2 are the roots of:

$$a_{11}s^4 - 2a_{16}s^3 + (2a_{12} + a_{66})s^2 - 2a_{26}s + a_{22} = 0 \quad (3)$$

It has been shown [18] that eq. (3) has no real roots and are therefore of the form $s_{1,3} = a_1 \pm b_1 i$, $s_{2,4} = a_2 \pm b_2 i$, $b_1 > 0, b_2 > 0$. Stress state at infinity is given by: $\sigma_{xx}^{\infty} = p \cos^2 \alpha$, $\sigma_{yy}^{\infty} = p \sin^2 \alpha$, $\tau_{xy}^{\infty} = p \cos \alpha \sin \alpha$ and the holomorphic functions are:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \varphi_0(z_1) &= -\frac{ir \left[\sigma_x^{\infty} + is_2 \sigma_y^{\infty} + (s_2 + i) \tau_{xy}^{\infty} \right]}{2(s_1 - s_2)} \zeta_1(z_1) \\ \psi_0(z_2) &= -\frac{ir \left[\sigma_x^{\infty} + is_1 \sigma_y^{\infty} + (s_1 + i) \tau_{xy}^{\infty} \right]}{2(s_1 - s_2)} \zeta_2(z_2) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

where:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \zeta_1(z_1) &= \frac{z_1 \pm \sqrt{z_1^2 - r^2(1 + s_1^2)}}{r(1 + is_1)} \\ \zeta_2(z_2) &= \frac{z_2 \pm \sqrt{z_2^2 - r^2(1 + s_2^2)}}{r(1 + is_2)} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

The sign ambiguity in eqs. (5) is removed by requiring $|\zeta_1| \leq 1$ and $|\zeta_2| \leq 1$. The complex variables are defined in terms of the real position coordinates according to: $z_1 = x + s_1 y$ and $z_2 = x + s_2 y$.

Finally the displacement components at Ox and Oy directions are given by [16]:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u &= 2 \operatorname{Re} \left[p_1 \varphi_0(z_1) + p_2 \psi_0(z_2) \right] + x \varepsilon_{xx}^{\infty} + y \varepsilon_{xy}^{\infty} \\ v &= 2 \operatorname{Re} \left[q_1 \varphi_0(z_1) + q_2 \psi_0(z_2) \right] + y \varepsilon_{yy}^{\infty} + x \varepsilon_{xy}^{\infty} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

with: $p_1 = a_{11}s_1^2 + a_{12} - a_{16}s_1$, $p_2 = a_{11}s_2^2 + a_{12} - a_{16}s_2$, $q_1 = (a_{12}s_1^2 + a_{22} - a_{26}s_1) / s_1$,

$$q_2 = (a_{12}s_2^2 + a_{22} - a_{26}s_2) / s_2$$

An example of an image that follows the applied procedure is shown in Fig. 2. It is worthwhile mentioning that the two images are almost identical and is very hard to identify the deformation by visual observation.

Simulations and results

The simulations were executed for the parameters of the synthetic images presented in table 1. The parameters of the physical model represented by eqs. (1)-(6) are shown in Table 2, The image scaling factor relative to the physical model was $100/25.4 = 3.937$ pixels/mm.

For each combination of parameters an initial and a deformed frame were generated and the full field of strain was calculated using MFRGM. Those values were used to compute the mean deviation of MFRGM results from the analytic solution as an expression of the error. Example fields of strain, for the analytic solution and the MFRGM simulated results are presented in fig. 3.

Figure 2: Synthetically generated images (mean dot distance = 27pixels, Total size=1600x1200 pixels) (a) Undeformed medium (b) Deformed medium.

Table 1: Synthetic images parameters

Image resolution	1600x1200 pixels.
Digitization Bit Depth	8-bits
Dot radius	6 ... 12 pixels
Dot transition	3 pixels
Dot mean distance	24 ... 100 pixels
Dot light intensity height	0.73

Figure 3: Strain distribution of simulation in fig.2 ($a = 5\pi/12$). (a) Analytic solution, (b) MFRGM Simulation results

Table 2: Physical Model simulation parameter values

$a_{11} (Pa^{-1})$	$a_{22} (Pa^{-1})$	$a_{12} (Pa^{-1})$	$a_{66} (Pa^{-1})$	$r (m)$	$p (Pa)$	$\alpha (rad)$
8.8495×10^{-12}	1.8975×10^{-11}	-3.9823×10^{-12}	3.5088×10^{-11}	25.4×10^{-3}	93.6×10^6	$0, \dots, \pi/2$

In fig. 4 (a) the mean deviation between the analytic and the measured strain components is plotted for various load angles. As expected the error is mostly

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 4: (a) Mean Strain deviation as a function of load angle for dot radius equal to 7 pixels. (b-d) Mean Strain deviation as a function of mean dot distance, with dot radius ranging from 6 to 12 pixels.

insensitive to the load angle, except the case where $\alpha = 75^\circ$, where it appears to be smaller. This behavior hasn't been explained and may be attributed to numerical roundoff error instability in the MFRGM shape function implementation.

The sensitivity of strain is made evident in figs. 4(b-d), where the mean strain deviation of MFRGM results from the analytic values is plotted, as a function of the mean dot distance. The value of this deviation is well below $1.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Strain} (= 150 \mu\text{Strain})$, with values as low as $25 \mu\text{Strain}$, for relatively dense grids.

Another interesting observation from these figures is the fact that the strain deviation is mostly dependent on the mean dot distance, rather than the radius of the dots. Incorporating the results in [14], where it was shown that for uniformly distributed deformation, the deviation was a function mainly depending on the dot radius, we can conclude that the main source of errors in this case is the Mesh Free approximation. The way to reduce this error is by increasing the density of the dots, which is equivalent to reducing the mean distance between them. This reduction in the error seems to be happening monotonically for the simulated problem and is constrained only by the requirement that the dots should not overlap each other.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In the present study the behaviour of MFRGM relative to its performance in measuring fields of strain in anisotropic media was presented. The analysis was performed for a imaging setup that involves 8-bit quantization (256 shades of gray). Combined with the results in [14], where the performance of MFRGM was analysed for isotropic media, we can conclude that the method can perform with an accuracy ranging from 1 to $20 \mu\text{Strain}$ in the case of uniform fields and in the range of 25 to $100 \mu\text{Strain}$ in the case of non-uniform fields of anisotropic media. MFRGM appears to outperform Digital Image Correlation (DIC) methods where the mean strain error for uniform fields is over $100 \mu\text{Strain}$ and has usually values of $300 \mu\text{Strain}$ or more [19, 20]. Unfortunately, to the knowledge of the authors, there are no published results on simulated cases of non-uniform fields of anisotropic materials for DIC techniques; hence comparison cannot be made for this case on the basis of synthetic data.

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